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International experience in establishing an effective economic security system

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***Abstract.** The aim of the article is to study the economic security of the agricultural sector, identify the main risks and threats to agricultural enterprises, and develop effective strategies for managing economic risks in the context of current economic changes. The article uses methods of analysis and synthesis of literature sources, comparative analysis of national and international practices of economic security, as well as systemic approach methods to assess the state of the agricultural*

sector and its interaction with other sectors of the economy. The research results showed that the economic security of the agricultural sector depends on many factors, including natural and climatic conditions, availability of financial resources, and the effectiveness of government policy. The article also reveals that insufficient state support and a high level of economic risks complicate the sustainable development of rural areas. Furthermore, the authors identified a number of methods and strategies to minimize these risks, including the use of innovative technologies and infrastructure development. Effective management of the economic security of the agricultural sector requires the integration of innovative approaches to production, particularly through the implementation of advanced technologies and infrastructure development. To ensure the stability of the sector, it is necessary to increase the level of government support and create favorable conditions for rural areas, particularly by strengthening the financial and resource base of agricultural enterprises.

Keywords: *Economic security, Globalization processes, Agrarian sector, Sustainable development.*

Закордонний досвід формування ефективної системи економічної безпеки

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***Анотація.** Метою статті є дослідження економічної безпеки аграрного сектора, визначення основних ризиків та загроз для сільськогосподарських підприємств і розробка ефективних стратегій управління економічними ризиками в умовах сучасних економічних змін. У статті використовуються методи аналізу та синтезу літературних джерел, порівняльного аналізу національних та міжнародних практик економічної безпеки, а також методи системного підходу для оцінки стану аграрного сектора та його взаємодії з іншими секторами економіки. Результати дослідження показали, що економічна безпека аграрного сектора залежить від багатьох факторів, включаючи природно-кліматичні умови, доступність фінансових ресурсів та ефективність державної політики. У статті також було виявлено, що недостатня підтримка з боку держави та високий рівень економічних ризиків ускладнюють сталий розвиток сільських територій. Окрім того, автори визначили низку методів і стратегій, які дозволяють мінімізувати ці ризики, зокрема, через використання інноваційних технологій та розвиток інфраструктури. Ефективне управління економічною безпекою аграрного сектора вимагає інтеграції інноваційних підходів до виробництва, зокрема, через впровадження новітніх технологій і розвитку інфраструктури. Для стабільності сектору необхідно підвищити рівень державної підтримки та створити сприятливі умови для сільських територій, зокрема шляхом зміцнення фінансових і ресурсних баз аграрних підприємств.*

***Ключові слова:** економічна безпека, глобалізаційні процеси, аграрний сектор, сталий розвиток.*

Statement of the problem. In the modern world, the economic security of the state is becoming one of the main components of its stable development, especially in the context of globalization processes and rapid technological change. The agrarian sector, as an important part of the national economy, requires special attention in the context of ensuring sustainable development and preserving the country's economic security. However, the high level of economic and financial risks inherent in agricultural activities requires the development and implementation of effective management mechanisms aimed at ensuring the stability and competitiveness of agricultural enterprises.

Analysis of recent research and publications. An analysis of recent research and publications on ensuring the economic security of the agricultural sector shows a significant interest in the role of public policy, innovative technologies and international experience. In the context of ensuring the economic security of the agricultural sector, considerable attention is paid to the research of such authors as Malik M. [1], who analyzes state policy and risk management models; Shpykuliak O. [2], who studies the introduction of innovative technologies; Yurchyshyn V. [3], who adapts ESG standards to Ukrainian realities; Krysanov D.F. [4], who studies the impact of globalization challenges; Burkin'sky B.V. [5], who works on models of sustainable development of agricultural enterprises; and Prokopa I.V. [6], who focuses on process automation and information security. However, the problem of integrating economic security at the macro and micro levels in the context of global changes and political instability remains insufficiently researched and requires further development.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. The issues of adapting existing economic security models to the specifics of the agricultural sector, in particular in the context of climate change and global economic fluctuations, remain unresolved. There is also a lack of comprehensive research on the integration of technological innovations into the economic security management systems of agricultural enterprises. In addition, an important problem is the creation of mechanisms to protect agricultural enterprises from external economic threats, such as

trade wars or political instability in the international arena. The authors of the article propose the integration of theoretical approaches and practical recommendations for improving the mechanisms of managing the economic security of the agricultural sector in the context of global changes and economic challenges.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (statement of the task). The purpose of this article is to study the main aspects of economic security of the agricultural sector and to identify effective strategies for managing economic risks in agriculture. The objectives of the article are to analyze scientific and theoretical approaches to ensuring economic security in the agricultural sector, to assess the role of state policy in supporting agricultural enterprises, and to develop recommendations for improving the economic security management system in the context of changing economic realities.

Summary of the main research material. Recent decades in economically developed countries have been characterized by a desire to intensify the processes of sustainable development, a key component of which is ensuring the economic security of the State. One of the important elements of the economic security system is the development of the agricultural sector. The performance of this sector is closely linked to the quality of the means of production, primarily land, which plays a crucial role due to its fertility, quality and location.

Agricultural activities are highly risky, and their results depend on factors such as natural and climatic conditions, the level of financial and material resources, agricultural market conditions, and government social and economic initiatives. No market system is able to provide appropriate conditions for sustainable development of rural areas without active participation of the state, in particular through redistribution of national income to support the agricultural sector.

Thus, a developed economy plays an important role in coordinating market transformations in the agricultural sector. It guarantees stable support for the sector aimed at reforming it, improving production processes and creating an efficient agricultural production system.

Today's national and international markets demonstrate the growing complexity of commercial operations, the active use of multi-component products and increased competition between companies. The processes of managing financial flows, capital, resources and personnel are becoming increasingly complex due to the increase in reporting, document flow and intensity of information flows. All this leads to an increase in the level of economic risks, which remain significant.

While fraudulent activities in business were relatively simple in the past, they are now becoming more complex and sophisticated. This is due to weaknesses in the management system, poor human resources, and difficulties in obtaining reliable data on companies or enterprises. In addition, the dissemination of biased or inaccurate information is a consequence of the dependence of a large part of the domestic media on the economic and political interests of their owners.

Thus, today's enterprises face both internal and external crisis factors. Among them are the following: reduction of working capital and difficulties in obtaining loans; changes in the activities and structure of the organization; reduction of wages and living standards of employees; underutilization of labor resources; conflicts between owners; increased cases of non-fulfillment of contractual obligations by counterparties and accumulation of debts; limited funding for economic security measures. Ensuring a high level of economic security is the key to stable and efficient operation of enterprises, which contributes to their competitiveness in the market [1-3]. The policy of developed countries is aimed at developing strategic documents that are designed to increase the level of security both at the level of individual enterprises and at the state level in general. In this process, enterprises play an important role in ensuring the economic and social development of the country, and their level of security largely depends on external conditions.

Realizing the importance of the efficient functioning of enterprises and the need to guarantee their economic security, many developed countries have taken steps to reduce administrative and legislative barriers in recent years. They have created

favorable conditions for business, in particular by providing tax benefits, financial incentives and creating an appropriate economic environment [4, p. 19].

On the basis of international experience, it is advisable to analyze the specifics of ensuring the economic security of enterprises at both the macro and micro levels in the world's leading economies (see Table 1). At the same time, approaches to ensuring economic security may vary depending on national, religious and cultural factors, but they are united by a common basis. This basis is based on several key principles: scientific knowledge serves as the foundation for future development; technology is the main tool for ensuring economic security; the responsibility of managers is to promote the development of science and innovation [2; 4].

Table 1

Analysis of Approaches to Ensuring Economic Security of Enterprises at the Macro and Micro Levels in the World's Leading Economies

<i>Country/region</i>	<i>Macro level</i>	<i>Micro level</i>	<i>Influence of national, religious and cultural factors</i>
USA	<p>Principles: Innovation and entrepreneurship..</p> <p>Mechanisms: Legislative support of technologies, stimulation of startups through government programs.</p>	<p>Tools: Implementation of ERM (risk management), active cooperation with research centers.</p>	<p>Orientation: individualism, freedom of entrepreneurship and on individualism, free enterprise and innovation as part of the American culture..</p>
EU	<p>Principles: Sustainability and digitalization.</p> <p>Mechanisms: Green Deal policy, business support through Horizon Europe.</p>	<p>Tools: Implementation of ESG standards, development of digital hubs to support small and medium-sized businesses.</p>	<p>Common economic framework, taking into account the national autonomy of member states, with a strong emphasis on the environment.</p>
China	<p>Principles: Self-sufficiency and technological leadership.</p>	<p>Tools: Close integration of the state with</p>	<p>Collectivism and state control, focus on long-term planning and geopolitical strategy.</p>

	<p>Mechanisms: Investment in innovation through government programs (Made in China 2025).</p>	business, export support.	
Japan	<p>Principles: Efficiency and quality. Mechanisms: Support for research and development of new technologies through METI.</p>	<p>Tools: Risk management through Kaizen, automation of production, partnerships with scientific institutions.</p>	Harmony-oriented traditions (wai) and a cult of responsibility to society.
Germany	<p>Principles: Technological superiority and industrial sustainability. Mechanisms: Development of industrial clusters and platforms 4.0..</p>	<p>Tools: Focus on quality (Mittelstand), involvement of small enterprises in technological innovation</p>	Focus on precision and order, emphasis on family businesses.
India	<p>Principles: Inclusiveness and development of the IT sector. Mechanisms: Investment in the digital economy, development of small businesses through government programs..</p>	<p>Tools: Use of outsourcing models, development of the domestic market.</p>	High influence of religious and cultural values focused on joint development.
Ukraine	<p>Principles: Integration with the EU and recovery. Mechanisms: Economic security strategy, support from international donors.</p>	<p>Tools: Digital innovations in the agricultural sector, development of export potential.</p>	Transition economy, combining national traditions with European integration standards.

Many countries are focusing on developing theoretical and practical approaches to improving the economic security of enterprises and creating favorable conditions for their operations. Significant progress in this area has been made by enterprises in the

United States, Japan, and Germany. Analyzing the best practices of these countries in organizing economic security, we can identify key effective tools: improving the legislative framework, implementing preventive measures to prevent threats, rational use of labor resources and active use of innovations in all aspects of economic activity of enterprises.

Information security systems in developed countries can serve as models for developing similar mechanisms in Ukraine. At the same time, the creation of such a system and the updating of information security legislation are becoming increasingly important. This is especially important in the context of growing computerization and active use of the Internet, where the population is not only a user but also an active participant in the exchange of information.

Establishing a legal framework for the protection of trade secrets and other confidential information of commercial value is an important aspect of legal support for business activities. In most economically developed countries, the legislation regulating the legal regime of trade secrets and defining liability for their misuse is highly developed.. These norms are formed both with due regard to national legal traditions and in accordance with modern international trade standards [5-9].

An analysis of the experience of economic development of developed countries confirms the generally recognized fact that the technological revolution has become one of the key factors that ensured the stable development of these countries. In the context of global competition, it is innovations that form the basis of economic progress and determine the essence of the concept of economic security. Economic security implies the existence of conditions under which the economy is able to generate innovative changes, maintain sustainable development and withstand external threats.

High-quality economic growth is achieved through significant structural changes, transition to an intensive model of economic development, increasing the share of knowledge-intensive industries, and upgrading production facilities through the introduction of resource and energy-saving technologies. Also important is the development of electronics and its integration into production and non-production

processes, as well as revolutionary changes in communication systems that ensure the transition to the information society. In developed countries, modern technologies have significantly transformed production processes. Economic efficiency has increased as a result of increased production and service delivery. Labor productivity has increased significantly, and the requirements for employee qualifications have become higher.

From the perspective of long-term development, an important advantage of innovation is the creation of jobs in new production sectors through the commercialization of technologies and the development of new products. In addition, innovation contributes to a significant number of patents in traditional industries that actively compete with high-tech sectors such as aerospace, computer, pharmaceutical, communications, and office equipment [10].

Economic intelligence has become one of the priority areas of foreign intelligence services, which in a broad sense includes a set of measures aimed at supporting the state's foreign economic policy and commercial activities of the private sector. In parallel with economic intelligence, intelligence services implement measures to counter similar actions by other states, including activities in the private business sector [11]. The common interests of the state and the private sector create prerequisites for special services to engage the security services of companies, private detective and security agencies to solve such problems:

- analysis of individuals from among the employees of foreign companies entering the local market if there are suspicions of their involvement in foreign intelligence services;
- creating conditions for the implementation of active measures by special services on behalf of private companies;
- control and detection of agents or representatives of foreign intelligence in the field of foreign economic relations.

To achieve these goals, for example, in educational institutions that train specialists for the security services of banks, companies and enterprises working with foreign economic organizations, students are required to familiarize themselves with

the methods of work of the relevant intelligence services. They are also taught how to identify agents of foreign intelligence services [12].

States strive to protect scientific, technical and other important information from foreign competitors by regulating the methods of information protection in the private sector. In the field of information security, the interests of business and the state often coincide. The joint work of public and private entities helps to strengthen geopolitical positions, the authority of the state and improve the welfare of the population. Information security systems of developed countries can serve as models for Ukraine. Their relevance is increasing due to the digitalization of society and the active participation of the population in networking activities. Protection of trade secrets is an important element of economic security of enterprises. An effective HR policy plays a key role in this process. The selection of personnel for security services should be based on a comprehensive analysis of the character, environment, professional skills, and even psychological characteristics of candidates. Material support for employees also reduces the risk of theft of valuable information, and moral influence increases their loyalty.

The state should support independent media that promote the dissemination of reliable information, helping businesses avoid risks. It is important to encourage cooperation between law enforcement agencies and private security companies. Establishing joint headquarters and involving reserve law enforcement officers in them will help strengthen information protection.

In many developed countries, veterans of special services working in business security services receive government support and favorable conditions for adaptation. This guarantees their contribution to the protection of national interests even after they leave the service.

To develop the business security system, it is necessary to stimulate the formation of non-state security structures at the legislative level. Involvement of business in the development of the regulatory framework will ensure its compliance with market needs and effectiveness in regulating business security.

Conclusions. Summarizing the results of the analysis, it can be stated that ensuring economic security both at the level of the State and at the level of individual business entities is a systemic factor of sustainable socio-economic development. The current challenges of the globalized economy, intensified by technological changes and digitalization, determine the need to introduce integrated mechanisms for protecting the information environment, human resources and material assets of enterprises.

An analysis of the best practices of economically developed countries shows the dominance of innovation-oriented approaches to building economic security systems based on the principles of rational use of resources, adaptability to changes in the external environment, and active involvement of the private sector in the development of security strategies. At the same time, an important aspect is the consolidation of efforts of state and non-state institutions in countering modern threats, among which information challenges and cyber risks are of particular importance.

In particular, for Ukraine, given its geopolitical and economic peculiarities, the issue of creating a regulatory environment that would ensure the integration of innovations into business security and create favorable conditions for business participation in the development of strategic documents remains critical. Only a synergistic approach that combines technological, organizational and legal dimensions will create a sustainable basis for protecting national economic interests and ensuring the competitiveness of Ukrainian enterprises in the global economic space.

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